

High Performance Composites by Reaction Hardening in Titanium Di-Oxide/Aluminum Alloys System

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ABSTRACT

In rutile type Titanium Di-oxide-Aluminum system, the reaction between both materials is slow comparatively. Therefore, three kinds of the composites refer to the structures, are obtained by squeeze casting depending on the fabricating temperature conditions due to the reactions. One of them is non-reacted TiO_2/Al composite, and then, the composites is found to harden gradually on the temperature range of solid phase of Aluminum. Hardenability of the composites, effects of alloy elements on the hardening and effect of inclusion in TiO_2 on the reaction are investigated. The summary is as follows in the works. 1) The non-reacted TiO_2/Al composites hardened gradually from Hv 215 to Hv 765 by heat-treatment in the solid phase. 2) In the composites, Mg and Si in Al alloys produce the reaction layer which are soft layer and hard layer due to the reaction products respectively. 3) The composites for the case of Al-Si7Mg(356.0) and 2090 as matrix are obtained enough hardening by heat-treatment. 4) It was found that the possible hardening of the composites is attributed to minute amount of Na in TiO_2 as inclusion.

INTRODUCTION

The composites availed of the reaction between reinforcements and matrix alloys have been recently come to remark in the field of MMC. Those are various properties and processing, e.g. RANXIDETM, DIMOXTM, XDTM, SHS, Compo.Cast., MA, Reaction squeeze casting, et al.[1]-[6] and some their modified processes. The reasons can be considered due to the possibilities of the practicality on the view of properties as composites and processing, versus the conventional MMC have not so proceeded to apply actually.

In the previous conference, we revealed that in rutile type TiO_2/Al system, the squeeze casting process produced three kinds of composites structures, depending on the temperature conditions[7]. And it showed further that one of them was non-reacted composite, was hardened by heating at the temperature range of solid phase of aluminum[8].

The reactive combinations of reinforcement and matrices makes the non-reacted composites as cast, then the composites is strengthened to react by heat-treatment at the temperature range of solid phase of aluminum alloys.

In the present work, the TiO₂/Al composites are examined about the hardenability by isothermal treatment, and the effect of alloying elements on hardenability was investigated from the viewpoint of the practicality. Furthermore, the effect of inclusion in TiO₂ on the reactivity between rutile type TiO₂ and Al was investigated by thermal analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Two kinds rutile type TiO₂ powder was employed in the experiments. One is practical grade and another is high purity(99.9%). The latter is prepared as compared with the former on the reactivity. These powders are very fine particle(0.1~0.5 μm) and almost spherical. The chemical compositions and the inclusion contents are shown in Table 1 and 2, respectively.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of practical grade TiO₂ powder

Al ₂ O ₃	ZnO	SiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Na ₂ O	Nb ₂ O ₅	SO ₂	ZrO ₂	K ₂ O	CaO	TiO ₂	(mass%)
2.71	1.03	0.56	0.19	0.2	0.15	0.08	0.047	0.01	0.005	bal.	

Table 2. Inclusion elements in high purity TiO₂ powder(99.9mass%)

Al	Zn	Na	K	Ca	Fe	Ta	Cr	Ni	As	Pb	Mg	Ba	(ppm)
25.0	1.5	7.8	0.3	8.0	13.8	28.2	12.3	4.3	4.7	1.8	1.9	0.3	

These powders are pressed to a certain form and sintered slightly as preform(Vf=40%), and the preform is conventionally squeeze-cast to fabricate the non-reacted TiO₂/Al composites at the lower temperature conditions (pouring melt temp. ≈973K, preheat temp. of preform≈253K, pressure of squeeze cast:100MPa). The composites are isothermally heat-treated by electric furnace which has good controlling(±1K), at the temperature range of 773K to 873K. The hardness behavior of the heat-treated composites at liquid phase of Al had revealed in previous work. Then the reactivity of reinforcement and matrix alloy in the composites are investigated by DSC. Especially, the inclusion in TiO₂ come to be a subject on the reactivity of the composites which used practical grade TiO₂, compared with high purity TiO₂, and therefore the effect of inclusions on the reactivity of the composite at solid phase of Al was examined. The inclusion and the quantity which considered from Table 1, is doped to high purity TiO₂, and the doped TiO₂/Al composites was fabricated and examined the reactivity as same. The heat-treated composites are measured the hardness change, and the structures of each composites are observed and analyzed by OM, SEM-EDX, TEM and XRD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

REACTION HARDENING BEHAVIOR OF TiO₂/Al COMPOSITES

The transverse section of the fabricated non-reacted TiO₂/Al composites was shown in Fig.1.

The specimens cut out from the composites and were tested for various treatments. When the composites were heat-treated, the hardness of the composites came to increase with time and temperature by reaction between TiO_2 and Al. The reaction hardening behavior of the composites are shown in Fig. 2 which is isothermally heat-treated at the temperature range from 773K to 873K which Al is solid phase.

It is remarked that the hardness of the composites increases with times from Hv215 gradually, and saturates to Hv765 at each temperature, eventually. .

Figure 1. The transverse section and the optical structure of the fabricated non-reacted TiO_2/Al composites.

Figure 2. Hardening curves for TiO_2/Al composites heat-treated at various temperatures.

The reaction products were identified $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ and Al-Ti intermetallic (mainly Al_3Ti) from XRD. Therefore, the reaction proceed as following equations

The compounds are produced and increase in the composites by heat-treatment. The hardness begins to scattered with hardening, that is about $\pm Hv50$ under $Hv400$ over, and it became finally about $\pm Hv30$ on the saturated hardness. The reason of the hardness scattering is thought some subjects. Al-Ti intermetallic increases the area in Al matrix gradually with proceeding the reaction, while $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ is merely increase as dispersion particles. The heterogeneous structures of Al-Ti intermetallic and Al in the process caused the scattering of

the increasing hardness. Additionally, the residual stress may be resulted in it, because the reaction cause to reduce the volume. Then, Al-Ti intermetallic as matrix is constituted from major part of Al_3Ti and small $AlTi$ or $AlTi_3$ near the saturated hardness in the case the volume fraction employed. Therefore, the hardness scattering may be due to their hardness and distributions near the final stage. Then, the kinetics of the reaction are attempted to analyze from the hardness curves by cross cut method. As assuming that the quantities of the reaction is proportion to the hardness in the composites, the rate of reaction can be Arrhenius-plotted versus the reciprocal of time.(Figure 3) The apparent activation energy of the reaction is calculated 257.0 kJ/mol from the Arrhenius-plots. Since the reaction is to be in solid state for the case, it was considered that the rate-determining step was diffusion process. Nevertheless, it is difficult to determine the step because the value of activation energy is close to ones of each diffusion, e.g. each self diffusion of TiO_2 , Ti in Al, O in Al_2O_3 [9]-[11].

Figure 3 The plots of the reciprocal of time to the X(rate of reaction) versus the reciprocal heat-treatment temperature T by the cross-cut method.

Figure 4. The change of the micro-structure of TiO_2/Al composites by heat-treatment. (a) As cast $Hv \approx 215$, (b) Heat-treatment $Hv \approx 400$, (c) Heat-treatment $Hv \approx 765$

The micro-structures are very fine due to the particle size of employed TiO_2 powder. The change of the structure of the composites by heat-treatment were shown in Figure 4. It notices that the layer of reaction products is not observed surround TiO_2 . Then the structure changed with proceeding of the reaction, and it was found that a mass transfer occurred there.

EFFECT OF ALLOY ELEMENTS ON THE REACTION HARDENABILITY

When the composites are applied to practical use, it is important to investigate the effects of alloy elements in matrix. The each effect of Mg, Si, Cu and Li on hardenability is individually surveyed in the present work. Then the reaction hardening of the composites for the case of Al-Si7Mg(356.0) as matrix was examined. Figure 5 shows the structures near infiltrate surface of the each composite for the case of Al alloy contained Mg, Li and Si respectively. In the case of Al-5%Mg as matrix, nothing was observed at as cast. The reaction layer was produced at infiltrated surface of the composites after heat-treatment. It was thought that Mg was segregated at as cast and proceeded the reaction by heat-treatment. In the case of Al-3%Li as matrix, the reaction layer was produced at as cast. Then, Si and Cu were uniformly distributed in the composites. But many soft spots were produced in the case of Al-7%Si as matrix after heat-treatment.

Figure 5 The structures near infiltrate surface of the composites for the case Al alloy contained Mg, Li and Si respectively. (a) $TiO_2/Al-5\%Mg$ as cast, (a') After heat-treatment of (a), (b) $TiO_2/Al-3\%Li$ as cast, (c) $TiO_2/Al-7\%Si$ after heat-treatment

The hardness distributions near surface of the composites after heat-treatment are shown in Figure 6. It is indicated that the reaction products produce soft layer for the case of Al alloy contained Mg. Then Fig7 shows in the case of Al-Li alloys as matrix. The hard layer was produced in the case. From XRD, the reaction products are $MgTiO_3$ and $LiTiO_2$ respectively. On the other hand, Si and Cu were uniformly distributed to inner of the composites not to segregate. After heat-treatment, the composites produced soft spot which is $Ti_7Al_5Si_{12}$ for the case of Al alloy contained Si and became to be more hard by precipitates of $CuAl_2$ for the case of Al alloy contained Cu. In this way, the hardening of the composites proceeds by the reaction between TiO_2 and Al. Effects of alloy elements is how these elements affect the reaction between TiO_2 and Al.

Figure 6 The hardness distributions near surface of the composites after heat-treatment.

Figure 7. The hardness distributions near surface of the composites after heat-treatment.

Figure 8 shows the reaction hardening behavior of the composites for the case of Al-Si7Mg (356.0) and 2090 as matrix by isothermal-treatment. The hardness increased with time from Hv 280 to Hv 700. It is considered that the hardening of the composites are practically sufficient.

Figure 8. The reaction hardening behavior of the composites for the case of Al-Si7Mg (356.0) and 2090 as matrix by isothermal-treatment.

EFFECT ON INCLUSION IN TiO₂ ON THE REACTION

While the composites were examined about the hardening behavior mentioned above, the reaction mechanism were investigated. Figure 9 shows DSC curves of the composites. In the experiments, the hardening of the composites occur due to the little exothermic peak (arrow point) which exist about 873K under the melting point of Al in DSC curve (1). However, in the case of high purity TiO₂, the little exothermic peak can not observed there remarkably. The composites were employed practical grade rutile type TiO₂ as reinforcement.

Figure 9. DSC curves of practical grade and high purity TiO₂/ Al composites.

Therefore, it had been recognized that the TiO₂ contained some inclusions such as Table 1. However, we have considered that the little exothermic peak is intrinsic reaction between rutile type TiO₂ and Al because of the reaction products which are Al₂O₃ and Al-Ti intermetallics. It has been cleared that the difference of the reactivities results in due to the inclusion in TiO₂. Then the composites fabricated Al and TiO₂ added individual inclusion were examined the reactivity. As a result it was found that 0.2 mass% amount of Na in TiO₂ caused the little exothermic reaction under the melting point of Al.

Figure 10. DSC curves of a inclusion doped TiO₂/Al composites.

The Na doped TiO₂/Al composite were confirmed to harden by heat-treatment. Consequently, the reaction of the composites at the temperature range of solid phase of aluminum are significantly affected by inclusion in TiO₂.

CONCLUSIONS

In TiO₂/Al systems, the new process was proposed. That is, in the reactive combination of reinforcement and matrix, the composites can be fabricated so as not to be reacted, and after machining, can be harden to be reacted gradually by heat-treatment. The results obtained here are summarized as follows;

- 1) The non-reacted TiO₂/Al composites hardened gradually from Hv 215 to Hv 765 by heat-treatment in the solid phase.
- 2) In the composites, Mg and Li in Al alloys produce the reaction layer which are soft layer and hard layer due to the reaction products respectively.
- 3) Cu and Si in Al alloys are uniformly distributed in the composites. Si degrade the hardness of the composites to produce soft spots due to the reaction product.
- 4) The composites for the case of Al-7Si(356) and 2090 as matrix, was harden from Hv 280 to Hv 700 by heat-treatment
- 5) It was found that the hardening of the composites was attributed to minute amount of Na in TiO₂ as inclusion.

REFERENCES

1. Lanxide Corporation. *Catalogue* (1990)
2. David Lewis III and Mrintyunjay Singh#, For XD™ and Lanxide™ in situ composite materials. *In Situ Composite Symposium; Pittsburgh. Pa., 21-36*(1994)
3. M. J. Koczak and M. K. Premkumar, Emerging technologies for the in situ production of MMCs., *JOM*, **45**, No.1, 44-48(1993)
4. J. J. Moore, Combustion synthesis of advanced composite materials. *31st Aerospace Sciences Meeting & Exhibit., AIAA/93-0830*(1993)
5. H. Nakata, T. Choh and N. Kanetake, Fabrication and Mechanical properties of in situ TiCp/Al composites by the interfacial reaction between SiCp and Al-Ti alloy. *J. Japan Inst. Light Metals*, **43**,152-158(1993)
6. H. Fukunaga, K. Kajikawa and T. Kakehi, Fabrication of Metal matrix Composites by Reaction Squeeze Casting. *Proc. 3rd Japan International SAMPE Symposium*, **1**, 931-936(1993)
7. I. Tsuchitori and H. Fukunaga, Process Control by Reaction Squeeze Casting for Intermetallics-strengthening of TiO₂/Al composites. *Proc. ICCM9*, **2**, 906-913(1993)
8. I. Tsuchitori and H. Fukunaga, Fabrication of particulate rutile type TiO₂/Al composites by squeeze casting and their micro-structural characteristics. *J. Japan Inst. Light Metals*, **43**, 26-32(1993)
9. D. A. Venkatu and L. E. Poteat, Diffusion of Titanium in Single Crystal Rutile. *Mater. Sci. Eng*, **5**, 258-262(1969/1970)
10. J. Grammatikakis, K. Eftaxias and V. Hadjicontis, *J. phys. Chem. Solids*, **49**, 1275-1277(1988)
11. Y. Oishi and W. D. Kingery, *J. Chem. Phys.*, **33**,905(1960)